

Studies on Aminonitriles. Part I. Preparation and Resolution of α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino) Benzylnitriles

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A few (\pm)- α -Aminonitriles of the type (\pm) R-CH(CN).NH.C₆H₄.COOH(*o*) (R = substituted phenyl or α -furyl) have been prepared and two of them have been resolved into (+)- and (-)-isomers. Their specific rotations have been recorded in different solvents.

WE have prepared (\pm) α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino)-benzylnitriles of the type (\pm) R-CH(CN).NH.C₆H₄.COOH (*o*) by condensing^{1,2} different aldehydecyanhydrins with *o*-aminobenzoic acid. The optical resolutions of (\pm) α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino)-benzyl and (\pm)-*o*-chlorobenzyl nitriles have been carried out through fractional crystallisation of their brucine salts to get the respective fully active (+) and (-)-nitriles. The specific rotation of (+) and (-)-nitriles have been taken in different solvents (recorded in Table 2). The introduction of chlorine group in phenyl nucleus enhances the optical rotations of (+)-nitriles.

Experimental

(a) *Preparation of (\pm) α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino) benzylnitriles*: Aldehyde (0.1 mole), was dissolved in ethanol (95%, 50 ml.) and potassium cyanide (0.1 mole) in water (10 ml.) was added, immediately followed by glacial acetic acid (0.1 mole) and the contents were stirred. Anthranilic acid (0.1 mole) dissolved in ethanol (95%, 70 ml.) was then added and the reaction mixture was kept at 20°-25° for 24 hr. The contents were poured in the crushed ice and the product obtained was crystallised from ethanol. The physical constants are recorded in Table 1.

(b) *Resolution of (\pm) α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino)-benzylnitrile*: (-)-Brucine (15.16 g.) was added to

(\pm) α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino) benzylnitrile (10.12 g.) in hot acetone (400 ml). The less soluble brucine salt (11.65 g.) m.p. 142°-143° was separated after 96 hr., part of which on decomposition gave (+)-nitrile $[\alpha]_D^{34} +54.19$ (l, 1; c, 2.03 in ethanol). This on further four crystallisations from acetone and chloroform gave crop E (1.2 g.) m.p. 155° which on decomposition gave fully active (+)-nitrile m.p. 167°, $[\alpha]_D^{34} +64.73$ (l, 1; c, 1.70 in ethanol) and $[\alpha]_D^{34} +65.48$ (l, 1, c, 0.96 in acetone). No increase in optical rotation was observed on further crystallisation.

The mother liquor on concentration gave a solid (12.0 g.) m.p. 128°-129°, which on decomposition gave (-)-nitrile $[\alpha]_D^{34} -14.29$ (l, 1, c, 2.1 in ethanol). This on three more crystallisations from dioxane gave a sample (1.09 g.), m.p. 140° which on decomposition gave (-)-nitrile m.p. 166°; $[\alpha]_D^{34} -61.22$ (l, 1, c, 0.49 in ethanol) and $[\alpha]_D^{34} -62.00$ (l, 1; c, 0.50 in acetone). The rotation did not increase on further crystallisation.

(c) *Resolution of (\pm) α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino)-*o*-chlorobenzyl nitrile*: (-)-Brucine (7.45 g.) was added to (\pm) α -(*o*-Carboxyphenylamino)-*o*-chlorobenzyl nitrile (5.38 g.) in hot acetone (150 ml.). The less soluble brucine salt (6.1 g.) m.p. 186°-87° was separated after 24 hr., part of which on decomposition gave (-)-nitrile $[\alpha]_D^{32} -29.85$ (l, 1, c, 0.67 in acetone).

TABLE I. α -AMINONITRILES OF THE TYPE (\pm)-R-CH(CN).NH.C₆H₄.COOH(*o*)

S.No.	R=	Formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %	
					Found	Requires
1.	Phenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₂ N ₂	167	87	11.0	11.1
2.	<i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₂ N ₂ Cl	177	93	9.8	9.8
3.	<i>m</i> -Nitrophenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₁ O ₄ N ₃	161	91	14.1	14.1
4.	<i>p</i> -Anisyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₃ N ₂	163	91	9.9	9.9
5.	<i>p</i> -Hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ O ₃ N ₂	145	84	10.2	10.5
6.	3-Methoxy-4-hydroxyphenyl	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄ N ₂	163	80	9.5	9.4
7.	α -Furyl	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃ N ₂	174	70	11.6	11.6

Note: All compounds described above gave correct Carbon, Hydrogen analysis.

TABLE 2. OPTICAL ROTATIONS OF NITRILES OF THE TYPE (+) AND (-)-R-CH(CN).NH.C₆H₄.COOH(o) IN DIFFERENT SOLVENTS

S.No.	Solvent	Dielectric Constant at 25°	R = Phenyl		R = <i>o</i> -Chlorophenyl			
			<i>c</i> (l, 1)	$[\alpha]_D^{34}$	<i>c</i> (l, 1)	$[\alpha]_D^{34}$	<i>c</i> (l, 1)	$[\alpha]_D^{34}$
1.	Methanol	32.63	0.96	+52.08	1.03	+ 72.83	1.00	- 75.00
2.	Ethanol	24.30	1.70	+64.73	0.88	+ 85.23	0.89	- 84.15
3.	Acetone	20.70	0.84	+65.48	1.15	+ 86.00	1.34	- 85.82
4.	Pyridine	12.40	1.37	+43.80	0.96	+ 62.50	0.97	- 61.86
5.	Ethyl acetate	6.02	0.90	+66.66	0.96	+ 88.53	1.32	- 90.90
6.	Chloroform	4.80	—	—	1.33	+116.50	1.10	-119.90
7.	Dioxane	2.20	1.36	+44.17	1.00	+ 85.00	0.90	- 83.35

This on further four crystallisations from acetone-chloroform gave a specimen (1.12 g.), m.p. 189°-90°, which on decomposition gave fully active (-)-nitrile m.p. 176°-77°, $[\alpha]_D^{32}$ -85.82 (l, 1; c, 1.34 in acetone). There is no increase in optical rotation on further crystallisation.

The more soluble brucine salt on concentration gave a solid (6.4 g.) m.p. 184°-85°, part of which on decomposition gave (+)-nitrile $[\alpha]_D^{32}$ +27.79 (l, 1; c, 0.72 in acetone). This on further two crystallisations from acetone-chloroform afforded a specimen (1.14 g.) m.p. 160°-61°, which on decomposition gave (+)-nitrile m.p. 176°, $[\alpha]_D^{32}$ +86.0 (l, 1; c, 1.16

in acetone). The optical rotation does not increase on further crystallisation.

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